

Fatigue Behaviour of Bolted Connections Applied in Racking Structures. Experimental and Numerical study

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ABSTRACT

Rack structures made of cold-formed steel have been used in industrial sectors, supporting and guiding S/R machines, which raises fatigue concerns. EC3 [1] has no reference to fatigue design of cold-formed thin-walled sections. For that reason, the FASTCOLD project was proposed aiming at providing fatigue design rules to be include in EC3, including bolted joints that are often used to connect rack members. This work presents an overview of the work performed as regards the fatigue characterization of bolted joints made of thin steel plates.

Metal steel plates 2mm thick made of S350GD steel grade, connected with M12 bolts (class 8.8, DIN933; Washer DIN125; and Nut DIN934) were tested experimentally, covering the following conditions:

- Single bolted joints, snug tight bolts (30% preload), punched holes, stress ratio, $R=0.1$ (ref. series);
- Single bolted joints, preloaded bolts, punched holes, stress ratio, $R=0.1$;
- Single bolted joints, snug tight bolts, punched holes, reduced net section, stress ratio, $R=0.1$;
- Single bolted joints, snug tight bolts, punched holes, stress ratio, $R=0.3$;
- Single bolted joints, snug tight bolts, punched holes, stress ratio, $R=0.5$;
- Multiple bolted joints, snug tight bolts, punched holes, stress ratio, $R=0.1$;
- Multiple bolted joints, snug tight bolts, drilled holes, stress ratio, $R=0.1$;

S-N curves were obtained in accordance with ASTM E739 standard [2]. Numerical simulations, using ANSYS R18.2 were carried out in order to predict the fatigue strength. For this purpose, the Ramberg-Osgood's cyclic curve available in the literature for the S355 steel grade was considered [3]. In addition, the fatigue strain-life relation available in the literature for the same material was used in the context of local strain approach. $\frac{1}{4}$ of the joints was modelled using standard surface-to-surface contact conditions, with the augmented Lagrangian algorithm and a constant friction coefficient, extracted from literature for zinc coated steel [4], were taken into account.

Figure 1 shows that S-N results show in general an average slope around 8 instead of 3 as suggested by EC3. This discrepancy may be due to the higher importance that cracks initiation plays in the bolted joints fatigue behaviour. The preload effect increases the fatigue strength as expected. Also, for lower loads, the failure occurred along the gross cross-section due to the clamping effect. Changing the R-ratio effect, but maintaining the maximum load, the fracture tends to move away from the centre. Reducing the net section (reduction of 10mm) caused an increase in fatigue strength, which is an unexpected result. Multiple bolted connections presented higher strength than single connections. However, specimens with drilled holes resulted in worse results than punched holes due to a low quality of drilled holes. The EC3 class 90

S-N curve results in safe predictions for fatigue lives above 2×10^5 cycles. For fatigue lives above 1×10^6 cycles the EC3 is excessively conservative due to the significantly different slopes.

Normal stresses and strains were evaluated numerically in the bolt holes (diametrical position), and it was verified that the average stress is almost null for a stabilized hysteresis loop (see Figure 1). Using a stain-life approach [3], S-N curves were predicted. It was verified that the predicted slopes of the SN curves are in agreement with experimental results (black circles). As the punching process may generate tensile residual stresses around the hole, that would cause a reduction of fatigue strength (black triangles). Assuming positive residual stresses at bolt holes vicinity leads to a discrepancy of results (conservative), but that may be associated to differences of material fatigue properties from literature and this study, and also due to the fatigue crack propagation disregard.

Fig. 1. S-N curves and failure modes: STB - Snug Tight Bolt; PB - Preloaded Bolt; S – Single; M – Multiple; PH - Punched Hole; DH - Drilled Hole; R - Stress Ratio; RS - Reduced Section. Numerical Models: A- Single/B-Multiple (Normal Stress XX); Stabilized stress-strain hysteresis loop.

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